

CONNECTION OF SCREEN TIME EXPOSURE AND CHILD REARING PRACTICES ON KINDERGARTNERS' SOCIO-EMOTIONAL COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

In an era of increasing digital engagement, more and more young children are exposed to screen during their critical developmental stages. Simultaneously, parenting approaches play an integral role in guiding children's emotional and social growth. This study aimed to address the significant connection of screen time exposure and child-rearing practices on kindergartners' socio-emotional competence, contributing to better understanding and solutions for early childhood development challenges. This study investigated the significant influence of screen time exposure and child-rearing practices on the socio-emotional competence of the (80) eighty kindergartners enrolled in the Division of Valencia City, Province of Bukidnon, school year 2023–2024. It employed a descriptive-correlational research design. Researcher-made instruments were used, content validated, and pilot tested to establish reliability. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the screen time exposure, child-rearing practices, and the kindergartners' socio-emotional competence. Meanwhile, Kendall's Tau was utilized to determine the significant association of screen time exposure and child-rearing practices on the kindergartners' socio-emotional competence. The results show that the kindergartners are highly exposed to screens, implying that they have more time watching TV, using smartphones, and other gadgets. Also, the quality of the parents' child-rearing practices is very good. The socio-emotional competence of the kindergartners is high, implying that they are able to build relationships and connections with other children. By integrating insights from developmental psychology and educational studies, this study aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for parents and educators to optimize child-rearing practices in the digital age. Findings are expected to contribute to a deeper

understanding of how digital and familial environments intersect in early childhood development.

Keywords: *Screentime Exposure, Child Rearing Practices, Socio-Emotional Competence*

INTRODUCTION

In the current digital era, young children are exposed to screens almost constantly, raising questions about the possible effects on their socio-emotional development. Simultaneously, early socio-emotional competency is significantly shaped by parenting techniques. These early devices, primarily focused on entertainment, laid the groundwork for the profound integration of technology into children's daily activities (Takeuchi & Stevens, 2019). As technology rapidly evolved, many parents found monitoring their children's growth and well-being challenging in this increasingly digital environment (Radesky et al., 2020).

However, the double-edged nature of technology created a gap between individuals' socialization and mental health. He and Garon's (2023) study highlight a worrying trend of children with prolonged screen exposure who are more prone to social and emotional difficulties, including depression and anxiety. This risk is exacerbated by the frequent use of digital media in family settings, underscoring the pivotal role of parents in moderating screen time and access to devices at home.

In their exploration of digital behaviors, Limone and Toto (2022) introduced the term "digitods" to describe children born after 2008. Growing up with portable touchscreen devices, these children exhibit unique digital behavior patterns that shape their early development (Dong & Mertala, 2021).

The preschool years, a critical period for psycho-social and cognitive development, have been profoundly influenced by increased screen exposure, especially during the pandemic's surge in online learning (Dong et al., 2021). Moreover, Wang et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of this stage, noting the brain's plasticity and vulnerability to the effects of digital overexposure.

Furthermore, this study intended to fulfill a specific gap in the expanding body of research highlighting the developmental risks associated with excessive screen time exposure, such as the findings shared by Dy (2023) that prolonged screen use among young children is linked to diminished language skills and diminished personal and interpersonal abilities. Although previous research has thoroughly examined cognitive and linguistic outcomes, little is known about how screen time exposure and parenting styles interact to affect kindergarteners' socioemotional skills. This study offers a localized perspective on how these factors interact within the distinct cultural and technical landscape of the Philippines by concentrating on important areas like motivation, empathy, and social skills.

This research, therefore, focuses on kindergartners' specifically on filipino children aged 5-6 years old. Moreover, this study investigated how the amount of screen time and the kind of child rearing practices they receive at home interplay with the critical areas of developing the socio-emotional competence specifically motivation, empathy, and social skills during early childhood. It also explored young children's involvement of screen time exposure to digital technology, their capacity to regulate their emotions, and their behavior towards other people. Clarifying these effects can derive informative guidelines around technology usage that optimize healthy socio-emotional development for young children in today's digital age. Diving deeper on child rearing practices, also provides vast understanding of its vital role in providing high quality and effective parenting techniques ensuring their children's holistic development. Based on the above scenario, the researcher then conceptualized the research problem.

Research Questions

The study aimed to investigate the significant connection between screen time exposure and child rearing practices on the socio-emotional competence of the kindergartners who were currently enrolled in a Public Elementary School, from the Division of Valencia City, located at the Province of Bukidnon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of screen time exposure among kindergartners?
2. What is the quality of child-rearing practices that the kindergartners experienced as assessed by the parents?
3. What is the kindergartners' extent of socio-emotional competence considering:
 - 3.1. motivation;
 - 3.2. empathy; and
 - 3.3. social skills?
4. Are the kindergartners' screen time exposure and their parents' child-rearing practices significantly associate with their socio-emotional competence?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design, which examines and documents the relationships between variables in their natural setting without introducing any manipulation (Johnson & Christensen, 2022).

Through this approach, the researcher could gather data using standard tools, analyze relationships between variables using statistics, and potentially apply findings to similar groups of participants, which helped achieve the study's goals of understanding how digital media use and parenting practices connect to children's social-emotional development.

The sample consisted of 80 parents of kindergarteners enrolled in a Public Elementary School in Valencia City, Bukidnon during the school year 2023-2024. Using Yamane's formula with a 95% confidence level, the researcher calculated the sample size from a total population of 153 kindergarten students. The participants were selected through computerized random sampling from class rosters across four kindergarten sections, ensuring equal representation from each stratum.

RESULTS

Based on the data gathered from this study, the following findings are thus presented:

1. Kindergartners nowadays were highly exposed to various types of screen implying that they have more time spent in watching TV, use their smartphones, laptops and other gadgets than reading books, playing and doing other daily chores.
2. Parents demonstrated very good child-rearing practices, indicating that their children experienced high-quality parental care.
3. Kindergartners demonstrated high socio-emotional competence enabling them to build relationships and connections with others across home, school, and community settings.
4. Screen time exposure among kindergartners shows a significant correlation with their socio-emotional competence development, though child-rearing practices demonstrate an even stronger relationship, indicating that parental involvement may be more crucial than screen time management in supporting children's social-emotional growth.

DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 1, displayed the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of kindergartners' screen time exposure. As evidenced by the overall mean of 3.51, the data demonstrate that their screen time was evaluated to a generally high degree. Given that the majority of participants (53.75%) indicated a high extent of screen time exposure, it is implied that kindergartners spend a significant amount of their time in front of screens. The results are consistent with previous research showing how commonplace digital media use is among young children (Tamana et al., 2019; Limone & Toto, 2022).

Research Question 1. What is the extent of screen time exposure among kindergartners?

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Extent of Screen Time Exposure among Kindergartners

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High Extent	0	0.00
3.51-4.50	High Extent	43	53.75
2.51-3.50	Moderate Extent	37	46.25
1.51-2.50	Low Extent	0	0.00
1.00-1.50	Very Low Extent	0	0.00
Total		80	100.0
Overall Mean		3.51	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.30	

As seen on Table 2, the data displays the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the parents' assessments on the quality of child-rearing practices that kindergartners experience. The overall mean of 3.96, indicates that the child-rearing practices were deemed to be of good quality, according to the data. This implies that the methods are generally thought to be very good, as evidenced by the fact that 85 percent of the participants assessed their child-rearing techniques as "Very Good". It can be further gleaned that 5 percent assessed their methods as "Outstanding," and 10 percent of them assessed as "Good." No ratings were found in the "Fair" or "poor" categories, indicating a generally positive assessment of child-rearing practices among the parent-participants.

Research Question 2. What is the quality of parents' child-rearing practices as assessed by the parents?

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Quality of Child-rearing Practices that the Kindergartners Experience as Assessed by the Parents

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Outstanding	4	5.0

3.51-4.50	Very Good	68	85.0
2.51-3.50	Good	8	10.0
1.51-2.50	Fair	0	0.0
1.00-1.50	Poor	0	0.0
Total		80	100.0
Overall Mean		3.96	
Interpretation		Very Good	
SD		0.32	

While, the Table 3 shows the summary table of the kindergartners' socio-emotional competence considering motivation, empathy and social skills. It can be gleaned that the kindergartners have high socio-emotional competence as indicated by an overall mean of 3.89. The data imply that the kindergartners have pleasant relationships with people around them. Notably, it is social skills that garnered the highest mean, though all domains were interpreted as high. These findings suggest that the students exhibit a strong level of socio-emotional competence, underscoring the importance of early childhood development in fostering positive emotional and social behaviors.

Research Question 3. What is the extent of socio-emotional competence of kindergartners as assessed by the Parents considering: Motivation; Empathy; and Social Skills?

Table 3
Summary Table of the Kindergartners' Socio-Emotional Competence

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Motivation	3.88	High	0.41
Empathy	3.88	High	0.46
Social Skills	3.91	High	0.56
Overall	3.89	High	0.44

Moreover, Table 4 presents the correlation result (Kendall's Tau) analysis if there is a significant connection of kindergartners' screen time exposure and their parents' child-rearing practices on their socio-emotional competence. The findings reveals that the variables are significant ($r = 0.173$, $p = 0.040$), indicating that the combination of screen time exposure and child-rearing practices significantly correlates with socio-emotional competence. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that kindergartners' screen time exposure and their parents' child-rearing practices significantly correlates with kindergartners' socio-emotional competence. Participants who received high-quality child-rearing also exhibited high levels of socio-emotional competence.

On the other hand, child-rearing practices showed a much stronger positive correlation with socio-emotional competence ($r = 0.657$, $p < 0.001$), highlighting the significant role of effective parenting in fostering socio-emotional skills. Parenting that is warm, supportive, and consistent greatly contributes to children's emotional regulation, social understanding, and ability to form positive relationships. These findings emphasize that while screen time may play a small role, child-rearing practices, influences the development of socio-emotional competence.

Generally, the results affirm that screen time exposure is significantly related to socio-emotional competence but has only a minor influence on shaping it. In contrast, parenting practices demonstrate a far more impactful and critical role in the development of a child's socio-emotional well-being. While screen time exposure shows a minimal yet significant relationship with the kindergartners' socio-emotional competence, its influence is more likely limited. Child-rearing practices, on the other hand, contribute a far more impactful and essential role in fostering a child's socio-emotional development, emphasizing the importance of effective and supportive parenting.

Research Question 4. Do the kindergartners' screen time exposure and their parents' child-rearing practices significantly influence their socio-emotional competence?

Ho. The kindergartners' screen time exposure and their parents' child-rearing do not significantly influence their socio-emotional competence.

Table 4

Correlation Result (Kendall's Tau) Kindergartners' Screen Time Exposure and Child-Rearing Practices with Kindergartners' Socio-Emotional Competence

	Measures	Screen time	Child Rearing Practices
Socio-emotional Competence	Correlation Coefficient	.173*	.657**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.040	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Conclusions

This study confirms Bronfenbrenner's Bioecological Model that child development is fundamentally shaped by complex interactions within their immediate environment, particularly highlighting how the quality of parental guidance serves as a primary determinant in children's socio-emotional growth. The significant correlation between child-rearing practices and socio-emotional competence validates the theory's emphasis on the crucial role of proximal processes - the sustained, reciprocal interactions between children and their caregivers - in fostering healthy development.

Building upon this theoretical foundation, the findings also substantiate Goleman's Theory of Emotional Competence, particularly in demonstrating how early childhood experiences shape emotional intelligence development. The high levels of motivation, empathy, and social skills observed among kindergartners who experienced quality parenting practices affirm Goleman's assertion that emotional competencies are not innate traits but learned capabilities that can be cultivated through appropriate guidance and support.

Drawing from these interconnected findings, significant implications emerge for early childhood education and parenting interventions. The stronger correlation between parenting practices and socio-emotional competence, compared to screen time exposure, suggests that educational programs and policy initiatives might be more effective if they prioritize enhancing parenting skills and parent-child relationships over strictly limiting screen time. This finding challenges simplistic approaches to managing children's technology use and advocates for more comprehensive strategies that consider the broader context of family dynamics and parental involvement in children's development.

Recommendations

Several recommendations are given in light of these findings.

1. That parents may:
 - 1.1. intensify high-quality child-rearing techniques that highlight motivation, empathy, and the development of social skills;
 - 1.2. create vast opportunities for social connections in order to prevent frequent screen time; and
 - 1.3. supervise and control their children's screen time and encourage activities that foster total development away from screens.
2. That kindergarten teachers may:
 - 2.1. provide more meaningful activities to improve the kindergartners' socio-emotional abilities by integrating real-life, skills improving activities such as role-playing and other interactive and fun-filled strategies; and
 - 2.2. establish a classroom climate that fosters creativity, collaboration, sharing, and respect as these are facilitative of developing a friendly learning community.
3. That future researchers may :
 - 3.1. consider conducting longitudinal studies on how screen time and parenting styles affect socio-emotional competence.
 - 3.2. conduct long-term research to explore the sustained effects of screen time and child-rearing practices on socio-emotional competence across different demographics and cultural settings.
 - 3.3. utilize both quantitative and qualitative methods to directly assess children's emotional regulation and interpersonal behaviors.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the study involved children below the legal consenting age, obtaining extensive guardian permissions was a top priority and an ethical imperative upheld by the LCREC. The researcher made sure to provide simplified verbal explanations of the activities before administering the survey questionnaire, ensuring that both the children and their guardians fully understood the nature of their involvement.

The principles of justice were upheld by ensuring fair analysis and avoiding stigmatization or bias when reporting results. Participants were given access to a summary of the findings in an understandable format, taking into account cultural and literacy differences. Throughout the study, the researcher's primary focus was on safeguarding beneficence, justice, respect for persons, and confidentiality, even above the importance of data collection.

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